

Efficacy of Lumbar Transforaminal Epidural Steroid Injections with Triamcinolone Versus Dexamethasone for Pain Relief in Lumbar Radiculopathy Due to Prolapsed Intervertebral Disc Herniation: A Prospective, Randomized, Double Blind Study

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Abstract:

Aims and Objective: particulate and non-particulate corticosteroids are used in lumbar transforaminal epidural injection (TFESI) for managing pain due to lumbosacral radiculopathy with varied efficacies and side effects. The aim of this study was to compare the efficacy of Triamcinolone and Dexamethasone in lumbar transforaminal epidural injection for low back pain due to disc herniation.

Materials and Method: This prospective, randomized double blind study was conducted on eighty patients aged 18-70 years of either sex having chronic lower back pain due to prolapsed intervertebral disc herniation. All patients randomly allocated in 2 groups (40 patients each) and received transforaminal epidural; Group I: Isobaric Bupivacaine (0.25%) 2 ml + Triamcinolone 40 mg diluted in 2ml 0.9% NS and Group II: Isobaric Bupivacaine (0.25%) 2 ml+ Dexamethasone 8 mg (2 ml). Visual analogue score (VAS), adaptation of Oswestry disability index (ODI), patient health questionnaire-9 (phq-9) and complications were recorded after procedure, at 24 hours, day 15th and 1, 3, 6 months.

Results: The VAS score was found to be significantly less in group I as compared to group II at 15 days, 1, 3 and 6 months after procedure (p=0.0407, p=0.0132, p=0.0001, p=0.0034 respectively). The % reduction in VAS score was found to be significantly higher in Group I as compared to group II at 15-days, 1-month, 3-months and 6-months. The ODI score and phq-9 score were found to be significantly less in Group I as compared to Group II at 1, 3 and 6 months after procedure.

Conclusion: Triamcinolone was found to be superior in pain reduction and functional improvements as compared to dexamethasone.

Keywords: Dexamethasone, Triamcinolone, Transforaminal epidural injection.

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Introduction

Lower back pain is one of the most prevalent causes of disability with incidence between 5 to 30 percent and lifetime prevalence of 60% to 90%. The common cause of lower back pain is lumbar disc herniation causing compression of nerve roots and backache that radiates to the lower extremities in a dermatomal pattern thus causing lumbar radiculopathy.[1]

The symptoms of lumbar radiculopathy include pain described as “electrical shocks” or “shooting pains”, numbness, weakness and tingling etc due to mechanical or inflammatory process, comprising atleast one of the lumbosacral nerve roots. Interlaminar epidural technique results in

deposition of medication in the posterior epidural space, but the disc or nerve root pathology occurs in the anterior epidural space. Therefore, nowadays, more importance has been given to target-specific fluoroscopically guided transforaminal injection techniques, which have the advantage of delivering the drug to the site of the pathology in the anterior epidural space and required lesser dose of steroid and local anaesthetic drugs.[2,3]

Epidural injections of corticosteroids are highly efficacious in pain management and are divided into two classes: particulate (PS) (triamcinolone acetate, betamethasone, methylprednisolone) and

non-particulate (NPS) (dexamethasone and betamethasone sodium phosphate). Particulate corticosteroids have a longer duration of action due to local depot effect which help in longer duration of release of drug at the injection site. But they may cause paralysis due to inadvertent intra-arterial injection causing an embolic effect and spinal cord ischemia.[4]

Non particulate corticosteroid are water soluble and contain no particles that exceed the diameter of red blood cells, hence does not cause any embolic effect but they are believed to elicit a shorter duration of analgesic effect compared with the insoluble particulate steroids due to rapid clearance and shorter duration of action.[5,6]

The aim of this study was to compare the efficacy of particulate (Triamcinolone) and non-particulate (Dexamethasone) corticosteroids in lumbar transforaminal epidural steroid injection (TFESI) for low back pain due to disc herniation.

Materials and Methods

After obtaining approval from Institutional research Ethical board (GU/HREC/EC/2021/1866) and written informed consent from the patients, this prospective, randomized double blind study was conducted on eighty patients aged 18-70 years of either sex having chronic lower back pain due to prolapsed intervertebral disc herniation at the levels of L3-L4, L4- L5, L5-S1 as evident from radiological findings on MRI. Patients were excluded from study who had contraindication to the procedure (active, local or systemic infections), coagulopathy, use of anti-thrombotic or anti platelet medication, history of allergy to contrast medium or injected medication, previous history of low back surgery, lower Back Pain due to any other cause other than PIVD.

Sample size calculation: Sample size has been calculated using software Epi info TM 7 with assumption of alpha error of 5% i.e. confidence level 95% and beta error to be 20% i.e. power of error to be 80%. $SD =$ (standard deviation in mean VAS in patients at 1 month) $=2.4$ and $d =$ difference in mean VAS score $=1.5$.

Therefore total 80 patients were included in this study and randomly allocated in 2 groups of 40 patients each by randomization using computer generated random number tables. Each group received study drugs as follows: Group I: Isobaric Bupivacaine (0.25%) 2 ml + Triamcinolone 40 mg diluted in 2ml 0.9% NS and Group II: Isobaric Bupivacaine (0.25%) 2 ml+ Dexamethasone 8 mg (2 ml) the total volume injected was 4 ml in both the groups.

Intervention: Patients were taken in operation theatre and a wide bore 20-G cannula was taken. Intravenous fluid of Normal Saline 0.9% 500 ml

was started. Patients were placed in prone position in the operation theatre. After sterile preparation with chlorhexidine, the area was draped and the skin anesthetized with 2% lidocaine. Using fluoroscopic guidance, a 23 G quincke type spinal needle was advanced in an oblique view to the safe triangle. Both anterior-posterior and lateral views were obtained to confirm precise needle placement within the intervertebral foramen at the 6 o'clock position under the pedicle. Contrast medium (Iohexol, Omnipaque) 1 mL was injected through a 10 cm catheter while being visualized in real-time fluoroscopy to ensure target medication flow and the absence of vascular, subdural or subarachnoid flow. After confirmation of absence of aberrant flow, patients were administered the study drugs as per group allocation.

The patients were shifted to Post anaesthesia care unit (PACU) after the completion of the procedure and were kept under observation with constant monitoring of vitals (heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, respiratory rate and SPO2) and any adverse effects for four hours.

Follow Up: After discharge, the patients were followed up telephonically and by subsequent visits to pain clinic for Visual analogue score (VAS), adaptation of Oswestry disability index (ODI) and patient health questionnaire-9 (phq-9) and for any complications at 24 hours after procedure, day 15th and 1, 3, 6 months. After 1 month if the patients had incomplete pain relief they were advised a repeat TFESI at the same level with the same type of drug.

Following data were recorded:

1. Demographic data: age, height, weight, sex, duration of symptoms.
2. Visual analogue score (VAS), adaptation of Oswestry disability index (ODI), patient health questionnaire-9 (phq-9) recorded pre-procedure, immediately after procedure, 24 hours after procedure, day 15th, 1-month, 3-months, 6- months.
3. Number of repeat injections.
4. Requirement of surgery
5. Adverse effects (hypotension, bradycardia, nausea/vomiting, vasovagal reactions and/or allergic reactions).

The primary objective was the comparison of efficacy of both the corticosteroids in reduction of visual analogue scale (VAS) at 1-month post procedure and secondary objective was to compare the pain relief at 3 and 6 months and requirement of repeat TFESI, functional assessment of back pain by adaptation of revised Oswestry disability index (RODI), patient health questionnaire-9 (phq-9) and adverse effects.

Statistical analysis: Statistical analysis was done using IBM SPSS statistics software version 21.

Continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation and categorical variables as absolute number and percentage. The comparison of normally distributed continuous variables among the groups were performed using Student's t test. Nominal categorical data among these groups were compared using Chi-square test. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant and $P < 0.001$ was considered highly significant.

Results:

The demographic characteristics regarding mean age, weight, height and sex were found to be non-significant in both the groups ($p > 0.05$). (Table 1)

The comparison of VAS score immediately and one day after the procedure were found to be non-significant in both the groups ($p = 0.2647$) but it was found to be significantly less in group I as compared to group II at 15 days, 1, 3 and 6 months after procedure ($p = 0.0407$, $p = 0.0132$, $p = 0.0001$, $p = 0.0034$ respectively). (Table 2)

The % reduction in VAS score after procedure was found to be non-significant ($p = 0.2855$) at immediately and one day after procedure while it was found to be significantly higher in Group I as compared to group II at 15-days, 1-month, 3-months and 6-months ($p = 0.0038$, $p = 0.0001$, $p =$

0.0001 , $p = 0.0001$ respectively). More than 50% improvement of pain was found in all 40 patients at 1 month in both the groups while the number of patients who achieved more than 75% improvement in VAS score was found to be significantly higher in Group I ($p = 0.0017$). (figure1)

The ODI score and phq-9 score immediately, one day and 15-days after the procedure were comparable in both the groups but were found to be significantly less in Group I as compared to Group II at 1, 3 and 6 months after procedure. (Table 3 and 4) The % reduction in ODI score and phq-9 score at 1-month, 3-months and 6-months were found to be significantly higher in Group I as compared to group II.

Three patients in Group I required one repeat injection while in Group II, five patients required one repeat injection while surgical intervention was required in two patients in Group I and in three patients in Group II at 6-months but the difference was statistically non-significant ($p = 0.644$). The incidence of hypotension, bradycardia, nausea/vomiting and vasovagal reactions were not statistically different in both the groups ($p > 0.05$). (Figure 2)

Table 1: Comparison of demographic characteristics in both the groups (presented as mean \pm SD or numbers)

Demographic characteristics	Group I (N=40)	Group II (N=40)	p value
Sex:	Male	22(55%)	0.822
	Female	18(45%)	
Age(years)	53.55 \pm 8.96	54.65 \pm 5.40	0.508
Weight(kgs)	69.65 \pm 8.36	71.37 \pm 12.88	0.48
Height(cm)	164.65 \pm 7.45	167.9 \pm 8.70	0.07

$p > 0.05$ = statistically non -significant

Table 2: Comparison of VAS scores after procedure at different time intervals in both the groups

Variables	Group I (N=40)	Group II (N=40)	p value
Baseline	7.625 \pm 0.86	7.4 \pm 1.17	0.33
Immediately after procedure	1.6 \pm 0.49	1.475 \pm 0.505	0.2647
1-day	1.6 \pm 0.49	1.475 \pm 0.505	0.2647
15-days	1.925 \pm 0.572	2.175 \pm 0.500	0.0407*
1 month	2.3 \pm 0.590	2.6 \pm 0.496	0.0132*
3 -months	2.65 \pm 0.533	3.25 \pm 0.669	0.0001**
6 -months	3.15 \pm 0.662	3.575 \pm 0.594	0.0034*

$p > 0.05$ statistically non-significant, * $p < 0.05$ = statistically significant, ** $p \leq 0.001$ = highly significant

Table 3: Comparison of ODI scores after procedure at different time intervals in both the groups

Variable	Group I (N=40)	Group II (N=40)	p value
Baseline	35 \pm 0.042	35 \pm 0.062	1.00
Immediately after procedure	34.55 \pm 4.30	34.1 \pm 5.92	0.6984
1-day	34.55 \pm 4.30	34.1 \pm 5.92	0.6984
15-days	27.45 \pm 3.36	28 \pm 5.53	0.5924
1-month	23.9 \pm 3.07	26 \pm 5.01	0.0266
3-months	19.65 \pm 2.93	22 \pm 4.25	0.0051*
6-months	17 \pm 2.64	19 \pm 3.54	0.0054*

$p > 0.05$ = statistically non -significant, * $p < 0.05$ = statistically significant

Table 4: Comparison of phq-9 scores after procedure at different time intervals in both the groups

Variables	Group I (N=40)	Group II (N=40)	p value
Baseline	13.2±3.42	13.97±4.45	0.388
Immediately after procedure	13.20±3.42	13.975±4.45	0.3882
1-day	13.20±3.42	13.975±4.45	0.3882
15-days	11.075± 2.94	11.27± 3.75	0.7965
1-month	8.125± 2.02	9.5±3.50	0.0345*
3-months	5.825±1.06	7.075±2.54	0.0052*
6-months	4.7±0.686	5.525±1.753	0.0070*

p>0.05=statistically significant, *p<0.05 = statistically significant.

Figure 1: Graphical representation of comparison of patients who achieved ≥50% and ≥75% improvement of pain (VAS) after 1 month of treatment in both groups

Figure 2: Graphical representation of comparison of post-procedural complications in both the groups

Discussion

Various studies have been undertaken for different steroid preparations regarding the microscopic size

of the particles and it was observed that the particles of dexamethasone and betamethasone were rod shaped, lucent, have low density and less tendency of aggregation with size of the particles

being less than 5 μm while the particles of particulate steroids (triamcinolone and methylprednisolone) were amorphous, opaque and could congregate into bigger particles of size more than 100 μm . The size of particulate corticosteroids could obstruct capillaries of diameter 5 – 8 μm , metarterioles of diameter 20 – 50 μm and arteries of diameter > 50 μm , causing infarction of that artery supplying the neural tissue. The size of steroid particles greater than 1000 μm cause faster precipitation and before administration of the steroid, shaking of the solution resulted in the formation of small sized particles that aggregated into bigger size and then got precipitated. Therefore, on entering the vessel it might be possible for any steroid particle to occlude any size of a blood vessel. [6,7]

Dexamethasone, which is a non-particulate corticosteroid, did not have any serious neurological complications but its efficacy is limited in patients with lumbar radiculopathy. Triamcinolone preparations have particles of intermediate and betamethasone preparations have the smallest size of the particulate steroids. Various steroid preparations have different physiochemical properties leading to unanticipated side-effects and results. [8]

Several studies have assessed the comparative effectiveness of different corticosteroid injections for lumbar radicular pain and found controversial results in terms of efficacy and adverse events.[4,9,10,11,12,13]. Present study demonstrate that the mean VAS score decreased from baseline value immediately and 1-day after the procedure in both groups but the results were statistically insignificant($p=0.2647$) which might be due to the effect of local anaesthetic infiltration at the site of injection in both the groups. The % reduction in the VAS score was found to be significantly higher in triamcinolone group after 15 days, 1, 3 and 6 months as compared to dexamethasone group. The number of patients who obtained more than 50% improvement of pain were not significantly different at 1 and 3-months but found to be significant at 6-months ($p=0.025$).

The number of patients who achieved more than 75% improvement in VAS score was found to be significantly higher in triamcinolone group than dexamethasone group (11 vs 1; $p=0.0017$) at one month and 3 month (2 vs 0; $p=0.000$) while no patients was found who had more than 75% improvement in VAS score in both the groups at 6 months. The present results are consistent with the study by Park et al[10] who conducted the first randomized controlled trial on 106 patients to compare the effectiveness of particulate (triamcinolone 40 mg) and non-particulate (dexamethasone 7.5 mg) corticosteroids in treating lumbar radicular pain. They found a significant

difference in reduction of VAS at 1- month in triamcinolone group as compared to dexamethasone group (2.4 \pm 0.9 vs 4.1 \pm 1.9; $p=0.000$). The proportion of patients who obtained relief from their pain was significantly greater in the group treated with triamcinolone than in the group treated with dexamethasone ($p=0.000$). They also found that reduction of pain score was higher in triamcinolone group as compared to dexamethasone group (71%.vs 40%). Therefore, they also concluded that TFESI with triamcinolone is more effective than dexamethasone for short term pain relief.

Similarly Bensler S [14] also found a significant improvement in NRS score in patients of triamcinolone group after one week and one month. They also found significantly higher proportion of patients receiving particulate corticosteroid reported clinically relevant improvements at one week (43.2% vs 27.7%; $p=0.001$) and one month (44.3% vs 33.1%; $p=0.019$). Madavi S K [15] also found superior outcome of triamcinolone in pain relief as compared to dexamethasone.

Kennedy DJ [14] also found better pain relief with particulate corticosteroid (triamcinolone) but it was not statistically significant. However, in contrast to our study, they found similar number of patients who achieved $\geq 50\%$ pain relief in both groups at 3 month (73% vs 73.2%) and 6-months (75.7% vs 73.2%).

Donohue NK[16] demonstrates the similar efficacy in pain relief and duration of relief up to 6 months between 10 mg dexamethasone and 40 mg methylprednisolone and also suggest similar rates of functional improvement between the two corticosteroid injections at 2, 3, and 6 months which was contradictory to our results. McCormick Z et al[17] , El-Yahouchi C et al[12], Rajkumari K et al[17] , Denis I et al[18] did not find any significant difference in reduction in VAS score between particulate and non-particulate corticosteroids at 1-month, 3- months and 6-months. These results were different from present study which might be due to different dose and drug used in their study and the impact of co-interventions (physiotherapy, osteopathy, occupational therapy, kinesiology, massotherapy, analgesics and narcotics).

Although the ODI score did not improve immediately after the procedure, however the % reduction in ODI score was found to be significantly higher in triamcinolone group as compared to dexamethasone group at 1-month, 3-months and 6-months. Madavi S K [15] found the ODI score significantly less in triamcinolone as compared to dexamethasone group (18.67 \pm 7.13 vs 35.83 \pm 5.10; $p<0.001$) at one month which was consistent to present study. Guven A [19] also

found significant decrease in ODI values at 1 and 3 months in the particulate group than the nonparticulate group ($p=0.013$ and $p=0.034$). Other studies did not find any significant difference in the ODI score in particulate and non-particulate groups.[4,10,17,18] This can be due to the possibility of inaccurate interpretations of the scale by the patients and that despite relief of radicular pain their responses may have reflected persistent back pain. Also, ODI, which was designed for back pain might not be sensitive to improvements in radicular pain.

Patient health questionnaire-9 (phq-9) score helps in diagnosis of depression and quantifies depressive symptoms with the intention to monitor severity over time. Significant improvements in pain and functional recovery also improved their phq-9 scores at 1-month after procedure and severity of depression was mild at 1, 3 and 6-months. The % reduction in phq-9 score found to be significantly higher at 15-days, 1-month, 3-months and 6-months in triamcinolone group as compared to dexamethasone group. So, the improvement of phq-9 scores were more with triamcinolone than with dexamethasone.

In the present study, three patients in triamcinolone group and five patients in dexamethasone group were administered repeat injection once in 6 months follow-up but the difference was statistically non-significant ($p=0.4560$).

Similarly, Kennedy DJ et al [4] found that the average number of injections received for each group was 1.6 for dexamethasone and 1.4 for triamcinolone. They concluded that patients who received dexamethasone required more number of repeat injections as compared to triamcinolone group.

El-Yahchouchi C et al[12] observed that 15.9% patients required repeat injections in particulate corticosteroid group (triamcinolone and betamethasone) while 4.2% patients required repeat injections in non-particulate group (dexamethasone) which was contradictory to the findings of present study in which repeat injections were administered more frequently with non-particulate dexamethasone groups while McCormick Z et al[20] did not find significant difference in the mean number of injections administered between both the groups by the time of intermediate follow-up (0.4 ± 0.7 vs 0.6 ± 0.9 ; $p=0.15$). They also found that particulate and non-particulate groups had similar proportions of patients who required repeat TFESI (27% vs 39%; $p>0.05$). Surgical intervention was required in two patients in Group T while in Group D three patients required surgery at 6-months follow-up. Though, Kennedy DJ et al [4] also did not find statistically significant difference in incidence of surgical

intervention in both groups (18.9% vs 14.6%; $p>0.05$) but they found that there was a less trend of surgery in patients receiving dexamethasone.

The incidence of hypotension, bradycardia, nausea/vomiting and vasovagal reactions were comparable in both the groups ($p>0.05$) in present study.

Although both corticosteroids have potent anti-inflammatory action, triamcinolone is more suitable for therapeutic options as it is theorized that particulate steroid preparations have local depot effect which constantly release the active drug at the site of administration over a longer period of time as compared to dexamethasone. On the other hand, dexamethasone is five-fold more potent than triamcinolone but it is freely soluble in water and rapidly cleared. Thus, theoretically, resulting in shorter duration of action in pain relief and less effective than a particulate steroid.

Limitation:

The sample size of present study was small and majority of patients achieved only 50% reduction in pain while limited patient had $>75\%$ reduction in pain during 6-months follow-up. Fixed dose of particulate (triamcinolone 40 mg) and non-particulate corticosteroids (dexamethasone 8 mg) were used in fluoroscopic guided TFESI. So, further studies on large sample size with RCT should be carried out to evaluate the efficacy and outcome in long term follow up and to determine the minimal dosage of corticosteroids for maximum long-lasting benefits with least side effects.

Conclusion

Transforaminal epidural steroid injections are effective treatment for low back pain due to disc herniation however the triamcinolone group had better outcomes as compared to dexamethasone group in pain relief and functional improvements as assessed by ODI score.

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